

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

Aliyeva Hamida Mukhtar

Azerbaijan University of Languages, Azerbaijan
 Department of World Literature and Literary Theory
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FICTIONALITY IN THE CREATIVITY OF CARLOS RUIZ ZAFON

Abstract.

The article identifies the reflection of fictionality principles in the creativity of Carlos Ruiz Zafon, and at the same time shows that the confrontation of Good and Evil, angel and devil constitutes the main philosophical foundation of his works. In Zafon's novels, angel figures are presented as symbols of fear and despair, far from the traditional benevolent image. The mythical characters he created often appear in the image of a "fallen angel", playing the role of the embodiment of evil. In works such as "The Shadow of the Wind", "The Angel's Game", "September Lights" and "Marina", the images of angels and devils complement each other, creating a fictional atmosphere. Zafon's heroes sometimes become agents of revenge, and sometimes "fallen angel" types who claim to be gods. The author also devotes a special place to the shadow archetype, artistically reviving the unconscious aspects of the human psyche. Through the images of twins, the metaphors of the mirror and the shadow, the dual nature of existence is brought to the fore, and the writer implements it with the principle of fictionality. In Zafon's works, heaven and hell, light and darkness are built on the principle of mutual existence. From this point of view, the problem of Good and Evil becomes the main structural element of her literary style and determines the artistic and philosophical content of his creativity. It gives us reason to say that Zafon creates a fictional narrative space between fiction and reality.

Keywords: C. R. Zafon, Fictionality, Angel and Devil, Fallen Angel, Novel

Introduction. Over the centuries, many philosophers, psychologists, writers, poets and artists have put forward various ideas on the understanding of the problem of the duality of existence and consciousness. In the initial stages of the formation of literature - in oral folk literature, folklore and myths, the understanding of the contradictory nature of man and the multilayered structure of the universe was reflected. That is why writers have pondered this problem since ancient times, and have also created multiple realities ("duality", "twoness" or "multiple world") and twin images in their works. The philosophical basis of the phenomenon of duality in literature is the ontological dualism of human consciousness, the ideas of ethical duality. Philosophers consider ethical dualism to be the root of many contradictions. One of the main reasons for it is that since time immemorial, an eternal disagreement exists between Good and Evil in the human soul. This feature of Good and Evil has manifested itself in different ways in fiction. One of the forms of this manifestation is undoubtedly the multifaceted embodiment of the image of the devil / satan. As an example, we can cite such images as Demon, Mephistopheles, Lucifer, Woland, etc. It is no coincidence that this duality is also reflected in the creativity of Carlos Ruiz Zafon. Thus, the writer presents the reader with a fictional narrative model in the form of good-bad, angel-devil. Calin-Andrei Mihailescu and Walid Hamarneh write in their joint book that writers provoke the reader with fiction with their "as if" and "what if" (Mihailescu, Hamarneh, 1996).

Unlike Romanesque art, where the supernatural character of the angel is emphasized, the Gothic genre emphasizes the protective role of the angel. The angels

created by Zafon play the role of fallen angels and appear in nightmares. As in the case of Zacharias, who torments the character of Jacinta in "The Shadow of the Wind", and Andres Corelli, who becomes Martin's nightmare in "The Angel's Game", they create a feeling of fear and despair in the heroes who see them. There is no doubt that this is done with the model of fictionality.

As in C.R. Zafon's work "The Angel's Game", it is possible to find the image of an angel in all his books. However, this mythical figure created by Zafon in his works is very far from the image of a benevolent, merciful, luminous and helpful angel that has been presented to us to this day. The images of angels he created have a negative meaning. These angels manifest themselves in a terrible form in the nightmares of the characters in the work. These angels also embody the image of evil, symbolizing fear and despair. In the work "The Midnight Palace", the image of angel and devil appears before us again as a symbol of destruction and revenge. It is also possible to encounter angelic images in Zafon's novel "September Lights". With the help of these mythical images, he creates an unusual atmosphere in the magical atmosphere. At the same time, it should be noted that in this work, the image of angel and devil merge and become a negative image. Thus, in an instant, the angel's wings turn into the wings of the devil, and his hands into clawed paws: "A huge silhouette rose from the shadows and spread two large black wings, resembling the wings of a bat or a demon. The angel had extended his long arms, consisting of two claws. His long and dark fingers were arranged alternately, and the sharp edges of his nails, like steel, shone in front of his hooded face. (...) There was more to this

frightening figure than mechanics. It was as if something had taken refuge inside him, turning him into a demonic puppet - a tangible and demonic being" (Zafon, 1995, p.176).

Also, in the novel "September Lights", the angelic figure created by Lazarus is described as a demonic creation: "... a metal angel, a giant with two large, black wings and a height of about two meters and with demonic pupils" (Zafon, 1995, p.128).

In Zafon's works, the angel and the devil seem to "melt" into each other, complementing each other. The image of the angel is always accompanied by the image of the devil. In general, the image of the angel and other biblical characters as antiheroes, the idea of identifying the angel with the embodiment of evil, is the basis of Carlos Ruiz Zafon's creative style. The characters of many of his novels – Lazarus, Kolvenik, Cain, etc. – play the role of "fallen angels" and fly high, destroying their own souls and seeing themselves as gods who can create new life from death. As an example, in Zafon's novel "Marina", we can cite Kolvenik, an evil force that can both resurrect and kill mice and people: "Kolvenik worked tirelessly. He recreated his throat and mouth. He looked like a monster. He gave him a deep, metallic and unfortunate voice. His jaw was supported by metal teeth. The soul of my beloved Mikhail was slowly burning in his own hell" (Zafon, 1999, p. 236). In another episode, Kolvenik is described as an unsuccessful imitator of the divine Creator: "Mikhail, you do not understand... You can't do the work of God..." (Zafon, 1999, p. 223). Sometimes these angels also appear before us as agents of revenge. We can see it in "The Shadow of the Wind". The character Coubert, who hates Detective Fumero, tries to destroy him by allying himself with the angel. In this part, Julian unusually transforms into his own devil, Lain Coubert: "With my eyes about to close, I searched for Carax, but I could not find him. In his place was another figure. It was Lain Coubert, whom I had learned to fear all those years ago, reading the pages of a book. (...) I saw how the faceless man grabbed Fumero by the throat and, like a toy, threw him into the frozen pool, the angel's hand pierced his chest, his damned soul evaporated, and his black breath, blinking and dying, fell on the mirror in frozen tears, his eyes resembling frost scratches" (Zafon, 2010. p. 548). As can be seen, Zafon uses the principle of fictionality in his creativity and, as the critic notes, "in the context of the literary work, real space and characters are fictitious" (Atamoglan, 2020).

In "The Shadow of the Wind", Carax, who became a classic symbol of dualism—both an unhappy lover and a writer who sold his soul to the devil—had amused himself since childhood by creating angelic figures with a wolfish smile. The work notes that on New Year's Eve, Julian would tell stories about the three wise men kidnapping the baby Jesus for terrible and frightening deeds. After a while, he began to draw images of angels with devilish smiles, and invent stories about disembodied forces that emerged from the walls and devoured people's thoughts while their owners slept. Torsa Ghosal and Alison Gibbons write that the boundaries between "real" and "fictional" are formed by what the writer presents (Ghosal, Gibbons, 2023).

As can be seen, Zafon also suffers from the same narrative principle.

In "The Angel's Game", it is also possible to see the angel and the devil in unity. First of all, we should note that the main character Andreas Corelli is a demonic character. In his image, we clearly see the image of the devilish angel. Since ancient times, we know that the devil has claimed to be "God". We can also see this claim in the image of Corelli: "Who did you want to be when you were a child, Signor Corelli? -God" (Zafon, 2009, p.292). Corelli also wore the emblem of the divine messenger - an angel - on his lapel in his clothes, and used this symbol on his business cards. In another episode, the devil, that bears the name Andreas Corelli, is partially identified with the angelic figure: "The director was already there. He saw him from afar, standing indifferently in the rain, next to one of the two large statues of angels at the main entrance to the cemetery. He was dressed in pitch black, and the only thing that made it impossible to mistake him for one of the hundreds of statues at the entrance to the cemetery was his eyes" (Zafon, 2009, p. 370)

As can be seen in the above example, the author again confronts us with the image of the devil, that merges with the figure of the angel and dissolves in it. It should be noted that in the work "The Angel's Game" the author directly speaks about the indecision of Good and Evil, about the duality of a single existence. When David begins to read the book "Lux Aeterna", which later turns out to be satanic, Zafon here again plays with words and leads us to a clash of seemingly incompatible concepts. The name of the book can be translated as "Eternal Light", which according to the Christian tradition can be interpreted as "Divine Light". At the same time, David calls this book "a kind of book of the dead" (Zafon, 2009, p.220).

The main method used by C.R. Zafon is the principle of fiction. It is no coincidence that one of his books is called "The Shadow of the Wind". Longxi Zhang writes that the main point of the work is not only the fact that the story in the work is true, but also the fact and fiction, reality and the difference between the text is also an important condition (Zhang, 2007). Zafon, following Jung, fictionalizes the unconscious of the human psyche, which is characterized negatively about the shadow. Here, the shadow can be assessed as an enemy, an "evil genius", an "evil / satanic couple" trying to control all of a person's thoughts and desires.

In the works of C.R. Zafon, the idea of the dualism of Good and Evil is seen in the creation of images of twins or "dead ring" (meaning "exact copy" or "one hundred percent copy"). Thus, a person always believes that there is a hidden force that controls his thoughts and actions, but also opposes him. Later, this force, borrowed from mythology, began to be called twin, soul, mirror, shadow, portrait, breath, etc. For Carlos Ruiz Zafon, heaven and hell are both polar opposites and concepts that need each other to exist. The connection between Good and Evil, angel and devil are among the main themes touched upon in his novels. The unity of Good and Evil crystallized in the metaphorical landscape of the author's artistic world and became one of

the main elements of his creativity, the motif and principle of the world model. The principle of fictionality in the narrative plays a key role in the creation of this model.

Conclusion. As can be seen, the creativity of Carlos Ruiz Zafon is based on the multi-layered manifestations of duality from an artistic and philosophical point of view. In his novels, the images of angels and demons are presented not only as religious symbols, but also as expressions of the internal contradictions of human existence. Motifs such as twins, mirrors, shadows, and the “fallen angel” depict the author’s heroes as possessing both creative and destructive power. Thus, for Zafon, Good and Evil, heaven and hell are not just opposite poles, but are essences that complement each other and condition each other’s existence. This duality becomes the center of the metaphorical system in his novels, adding depth to the psychological and aesthetic layers of his works. Zafon’s artistic world shows that the contradictions in human nature remain one of the main themes of literature, and through these dualities he expresses both individual and universal human experience with artistic fictionality.

References

1. Carlos, R.Z. (2010). *La Sombra del Viento*. Vintage Espanol.
2. Carlos, R.Z. (1995). *Luces de septiembre*. Editorial Planeta.
3. Carlos, R.Z. (2009). *The Angel's Game*. Vintage.
4. Carlos, R.Z. (1999). *Marina*. FISCHER Taschenbuch.
5. Atamoglan, A. Y. (2020). Fictionality in A Postmodern Novels (Based on the Creativity of Jasper Fforde). *International Journal of Innovative Technologies in Social Science*, 28(7). https://doi.org/10.31435/rsglobal_ijitss/30122020/729
6. *Fictionality and Multimodal Narratives* (2023). Ed.: Torsa Ghosal and Alison Gibbons. University of Nebraska Press.
7. *Fiction Updated*. (1996). *Theories of Fictionality, Narratology, and Poetics*. Ed.: Calin-Andrei Mihailescu, Walid Hamarneh. University of Toronto Press.
8. Zhang L. (2007). *History and Fictionality: Insights and Limitations of a Literary Perspective*.